

Academic performance of university students in a transdisciplinary bachelor's degree ^{*}

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Abstract. The Bachelor's degree in Service Science, Management and Engineering is a transdisciplinary proposal that attracts students from different secondary school modalities, which cause an apparent disparity of knowledge upon entry that would be affecting their academic performance. Using a monitoring strategy the new students were monitored during their first year of study. As a result, it was possible to characterize the students' performance according to their modality and to propose types of instruments to improve it according to the detected needs.

Keywords: Students' performance · Service sector · Monitoring strategy.

1 Introduction

In recent years, according to World Bank data [1], the employment in the service sector has increased in more than half of the countries in the world. Situation that led to the creation of the discipline Service Science Management and Engineering (SSME) whose objective is to improve the quality and productivity of service organizations through the contribution of knowledge about the concept of service and the training of professionals in the area. This discipline encompasses transversal knowledge of business management, information and communication technologies, engineering and social sciences, integrating them to give rise to a new knowledge that covers the skills required by service professionals.

Since 2014 the Rey Juan Carlos University (URJC) offers a Bachelor's degree in SSME. The curriculum design was the result of collaborative work between the URJC and expert companies in the sector (IBM, EULEN and MELIA) [2]. Its objective is the training of professionals in SSME with the capacity to conceive, design, build, operate, maintain and manage services from different sectors throughout their life cycle: from conception to after-sale [3]. Therefore,

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the formation of the degree revolves around the concept of services from different points of view such as computer skills, communications, business, marketing, among others. In this way, a holistic and integral vision of the service and the service systems is obtained. The related subjects are grouped into six modules: Fundamentals, Technology, Companies, Services, Social and Personal skills.

The fact that the Bachelor's degree in SSME is transdisciplinary makes it attractive for a wide variety of students from different secondary school modalities, who enter with an apparent disparity of knowledge due to their basic training. Consequently, starting from the premise that the different secondary school modality can be a determining factor in the performance of the student in the different modules, it was decided to monitor the performance of the new students of SSME during their first year. The results obtained allowed: 1) characterize the students of the different modalities according to the performance achieved in the modules of the degree; and 2) propose types of instruments to improve performance when necessary. Such results could be used in the future to measure quantitatively the impact of the instruments used and to think about a predictive model that allows the university proactively (with their knowledge of the number of students from each of the modalities) to propose the appropriate instruments to help the new students to improve their performance.

2 Methodology

The present work is a quantitative and longitudinal study that measured the relationship between the new students of the different secondary school modality and their academic performance in the first year of degree. During three consecutive school cycles, performance was studied according to the yields attained in the different modules based on attributes that evaluate the grades obtained, the approval effectiveness and the progress in the degree. All the students enrolled participated in the evaluation. Therefore, the official data of 21 students in the 2014-15/2016-17 school years and 28 students in the 2015-16 cycle were obtained. The studied modalities were *Humanities and Social Sciences* (HySs) and *Science and Technology* (S&T), discarding *Arts* because only one student was registered. The data were grouped by modality and year of admission.

The monitoring was carried out using the Goal-Oriented Context-Aware Measurement, Evaluation and Monitoring strategy [4], which has three capacities: 1) a formally defined process that guarantees repeatability and reproducibility of activities [4]; 2) a methodological support that indicates how to implement each activity of the process; and 3) a conceptual framework supported by a measurement and evaluation ontology that promotes the specification of the necessary metadata so that the results are consistent and comparable, avoiding inaccuracies when communicating or analyzing them [5]. The activities carried out were: 1) The *definition of non-functional requirements* that specified the need for information, the context and the evaluation model. 2) The *design of the measurement, evaluation and analysis* that defined the metrics and indicators, the decision criteria and the analysis that can be applied according to the scale

of the values obtained. 3) The *implementation of the measurement, evaluation and analysis* that allowed obtaining the results from what was specified before. For reasons of space it is not possible to include in this extended abstract a detail of the analyzes performed but more information can be found in [6].

3 Results

Characterization of the modalities: In **HySs** there is a negative tendency in the performance of the subjects of all the modules except in Services where there was a slight improvement. Its average performance in the modules was higher than 76%, with a variability of 11.79 points calculated as the difference between the average yield with the highest value (Services with 88.58%) and the worst value (Companies with 76.79%). The rest of the modules presented values of 77.46% in Personal skills, 76.82% in Fundamentals, 81.43% in Technology and 85.62% in Social. The modules with less variation are those of Services, Technology and Social which suggests that the new students of this modality present a better performance in them. In **S&T** there is a negative trend in the performance of the Technology and Companies modules, in contrast to the rest of the modules that show a positive trend. Its average performance in the modules was higher than 80%, with a variability of 8.49 points calculated as the difference between the average performance in the Social module with 89.37% and Personal skills with 80.88%. The rest of the modules presented values of 81.12% in Fundamentals, 82.06% in Technology, 83.03% in Companies and 87.03% in Services. The modules with less variation are those of Social, Fundamentals, Services and Companies which suggest that the new students of this modality have a better performance in the Social and Services as opposed to the rest of the modules. *Future guidelines:* It is necessary to apply instruments to improve the grades of the students of **HySs** in the subjects of the modules of Companies, Technology and Social, while in the **S&T** they are necessary in Personal skills and Companies. Regarding instruments that help to increase the level of approval effectiveness, they should focus on the **HySs** students in the Personal skills module. Instruments aimed at improving progress are needed in the **HySs** modality in the Fundamentals, Personal skills and Technology modules, while in the **S&T** they are required in the subjects of the Fundamentals and Technology modules.

4 Conclusion

The monitoring carried out does not show great differences in the performance of the **HySs** and **S&T** students but it does suggest that the **S&T** students have a better performance in all the modules except in Services. Beyond this better performance, the results suggest that the grades obtained are always superior in the **HySs** modality but their performance is marred by their level of approval effectiveness and progress lower. These results also provided information on the types of instruments that should be used to improve performance. The same monitoring strategy will be used to quantitatively measure the impact on

performance after using such instruments. The limitation that was found is the low number of students coming from the Arts modality that did not allow any analysis.

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